

**Highly efficient fused ring electron acceptors based on a
new undecacyclic core**

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Dear editor,

Thank you very much for inviting us to write and submit this article entitled “Highly efficient fused ring electron acceptors based on a new undecacyclic core”.

Recently, fused ring electron acceptors (FREAs) have attracted considerable attention and exhibit excellent photovoltaic performance, due to the merits of strong absorption in visible/NIR region, good energy level tunability, diverse and facile chemical modification to adjust molecular properties, and proper miscibility with donor materials.

Extending the π -conjugation of fused ring donor unit in the center of FREAs can improve its electron-donating capacity to reinforce the intramolecular charge transfer effect for narrower bandgap and enhance the intermolecular interaction to facilitate molecular packing for higher electron mobility, thus promising to achieve high J_{SC} and FF in organic solar cells (OSCs). However, only a handful of large fused ring donor cores have been developed and used as building blocks to synthesize FREAs so far. And there still remains much room to further improve the efficiency of OSCs based on them.

In this work, we developed two FREAs, IUIC-O and IUIC-T, based on an undecacyclic donor core with different side chains. IUIC-T having 2D conjugated side chains possesses higher extinction coefficient than IUIC-O. Blended with the donor PBDB-T, IUIC-T based OSCs achieve a higher PCE of 13.05% with a much higher J_{SC} , due to the aligned energy level with PBDB-T for efficient exciton dissociation, finer nanoscale phase separation and more orderly molecule packing in the blend for charge transport. However, the PBDB-T:IUIC-O OSC obtains an inferior PCE of 7.66%, mainly due to the too small HOMO energy level off-set between IUIC-O and PBDB-T

for inefficient charge dissociation. In fact, IUIC-T is among the highest efficiency FREAs having such large donor core. It demonstrates that developing large fused ring donor core is an efficient method to construct high-performance FREAs and 2D conjugated side chains can efficiently improve the photovoltaic performance of FREAs. Therefore, we believe this work will be of particular interest to readers of *Materials Chemistry Frontiers*.

We ensure that this manuscript is not under consideration for publication and has not been published elsewhere in any medium including electronic journals and computer databases of a public nature.

Sincerely yours,

Chun-Ru Wang

COMMUNICATION

Highly efficient fused ring electron acceptors based on a new undecacyclic core

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Two FREAs, IUIC-O and IUIC-T, based on an undecacyclic core were developed. IUIC-T having higher extinction coefficient, affords aligned energy levels with PBDB-T, finer nanoscale morphology and more orderly molecular stacking, thus achieving more efficient exciton dissociation and charge transport. Therefore, PBDB-T:IUIC-T based OSC gains a higher PCE of 13.05%.

Introduction

Organic solar cells (OSCs) show great potential to solve/relieve current energy crisis and have always attracted considerable attention due to the merits of low-cost, light-weight, mechanical flexibility, large-area fabrication and so on.^{1,2} Donor (D):acceptor (A) bulk heterojunction structure of the active layer of OSCs achieves great success, since it significantly increases the D/A interfacial area to circumvent the problem of short exciton diffusion length for the limited exciton lifetime.^{3,4} Among acceptor materials, fullerene derivatives have dominated the bulk heterojunction OSCs for almost two decades.⁵⁻⁹ However, this situation has changed since 2015, due to the rapid development of non-fullerene acceptors, especially fused ring electron acceptors (FREAs).¹⁰⁻¹³ Up to date, the power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of the FREA based OSCs have reached 18%,¹⁴⁻¹⁶ which are much higher than the best fullerene based ones (~12%)¹⁷. The quick development of FREAs benefits from their unique structural feature, which consists of a fused ring donor moiety in the center, side chains hanging out of the molecular plane and two compact strong electron-withdrawing groups at both ends.¹⁸ And these three components can be independently modified, providing

greatly synthetic flexibility and thus easily tunable optical, electronic and morphological properties. The intense intramolecular charge transfer effect between the donor moiety and electron-withdrawing groups makes FREA possess strong absorption in visible/near-infrared region, which contributes to sunlight harvest for high short-circuit current density (J_{sc}) in devices. In addition, the FREA based OSCs can work efficiently with small energy loss (E_{loss}), which helps to achieve high open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) without sacrificing J_{sc} and fill factor (FF) of devices. As a result, numerous high performance FREAs were developed and the PCEs of FREA based OSCs increase continuously, which greatly boosts the advance of OSCs.

Extending π -conjugation of the donor moiety in FREAs can efficiently reduce the bandgap for enhanced absorption, improve the electron-donating capability for uplifted energy levels and reinforce intermolecular interaction for higher electron mobility. Thus FREAs having large π -conjugation donor moiety for high-efficiency OSCs can be expected.^{19,20} For instance, by extending the donor core from

Fig. 1 The chemical structures and PCEs of decacyclic or undecacyclic based FREAs.

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Fig. 2 The chemical structures of PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T.

hexacyclic based IHIC2 to octacyclic based IOIC2 and even to decacyclic based IDCIC, their absorption onset shows redshift from 745 nm to 801 nm and to 853 nm, and the J_{SC} of the corresponding devices increases from 16.1 mA cm⁻² to 19.7 mA cm⁻² and to 21.98 mA cm⁻², successively.^{19, 20} Simultaneously, the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) energy level of the FREAs also up-shifts by extending the donor core, which helps to achieve higher V_{OC} . Therefore, the PCEs of OSCs based on IHIC2, IOIC2 and IDCIC increase from 7.31% to 12.3% and to 13.58%, successively. However, there are only a handful of decacyclic or undecacyclic based FREAs reported so far²⁰⁻²³. The chemical structures and their photovoltaic performance are summarized in Fig. 1. Therefore, more efforts should be taken to develop large donor moiety based FREAs and further improve the efficiencies of OSCs. In addition, introducing conjugated side chains can extend intramolecular conjugation for enhanced light absorption and J_{SC} . And two-dimensional (2D) conjugation also facilitates charge transport, due to the promoted π - π overlap and intermolecular interaction.^{24, 25} This strategy has been widely applied in donor materials, but rarely reported in acceptors.^{26, 27}

In this article, we combine the extending fused-ring donor core and 2D conjugation strategy together to design highly efficient FREAs. Based on a new undecacyclic core, two FREAs, IUIC-O and IUIC-T, were developed (Fig. 2). Both FREAs show strong absorption in Vis-NIR region and good molecular stacking. Highly efficient polymer, PBDB-T, which possesses complementary absorption, was chosen as the donor to fabricate OSCs with them. The exciton dissociation, charge transport and morphology of the devices were investigated. The PBDB-T:IUIC-T based OSC achieves a PCE of 13.05% which is much higher than PBDB-T:IUIC-O based one (7.66%), mainly due to its stronger absorption, more efficient exciton dissociation, finer nanoscale phase separation and better molecular packing in blend film for higher mobility, thus higher J_{SC} in the PBDB-T:IUIC-T device.

Results and discussion

The synthetic routes of IUIC-O and IUIC-T are shown in Scheme S1 and their synthetic details are presented in the Supporting Information (ESI[†]). The solution and thin-film absorption spectra of IUIC-O and IUIC-T are shown in Fig. S3 and Fig. 3, respectively. The corresponding optical data are summarized in Table S1. In solution, both IUIC-O and IUIC-T demonstrate strong absorption in the range of 600-850 nm. The maximum absorption peak of IUIC-O is located at 768 nm, which is slightly redshifted compared to IUIC-T. This is ascribed to the stronger electron-donating capacity of alkoxy side chains than alkyl-thienyl substitutes. However, the maximum extinction coefficient of IUIC-T is higher than that of IUIC-O (2.1×10^5

Fig. 3 Absorption spectra of PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T thin films.

M⁻¹ cm⁻¹ vs 1.8×10^5 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), which results from the superior conjugation effect of alkyl-thienyl substitutes on the backbone. Compared with the absorption of their solutions, the maximum absorption peaks of IUIC-O and IUIC-T films show remarkable redshift from 768 to 812 nm and from 757 to 795 nm, respectively, which implies the compact molecular stacking in the solid state of IUIC-O and IUIC-T. The optical gaps of IUIC-O and IUIC-T, estimated from the absorption onset of the thin film, are 1.34 and 1.37 eV, respectively. And the classic wide band-gap polymer PBDB-T was chosen as the donor, which possesses strong absorption in the range of 300-650 nm.²⁸ The complementary absorption between the donor and acceptors, as shown in Fig. 3, would offer good opportunity for high J_{SC} .

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was employed to evaluate the energy levels of IUIC-O, IUIC-T and PBDB-T (Fig. S4). According to the empirical equation, the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) energy levels of IUIC-O, IUIC-T and PBDB-T were calculated to be -5.16 eV, -5.26 eV and -5.16 eV, respectively. The small HOMO offsets between the donor and acceptors would promise to low E_{loss} . The LUMO energy levels of IUIC-O, IUIC-T and PBDB-T were calculated to be -3.93 eV, -3.92 eV and -3.02 eV, respectively. IUIC-O and IUIC-T present almost the same LUMO energy levels, indicating that side chains on the donor moiety have negligible influence on the LUMO energy level of FREAs. Because of the stronger electron-donating capacity of alkoxy than alkyl-thienyl, IUIC-O offers shallower HOMO energy level and thus narrower bandgap than IUIC-T, which is consistent with their optical bandgaps.

The inverted OSCs with a structure of ITO/ZnO/PBDB-T:FREA/MoO₃/Ag were fabricated to investigate the photovoltaic performance of IUIC-O and IUIC-T. The J - V curves and corresponding photovoltaic parameters are shown in Fig. 4a and Table 1,

Fig. 4 (a) J - V curves and (b) EQE spectra of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T based inverted OSCs.

Table 1 Performance data for PBDB-T:FREA inverted OSCs.

Donor:FREA	V_{oc} [V]	J_{sc} [mA cm^{-2}]	FF	PCE [%]
PBDB-T:IUIC-O	0.81	13.7	0.69	7.66
PBDB-T:IUIC-T	0.84	22.2	0.70	13.05

respectively. The IUIC-T based OSCs afford a PCE as high as 13.05%, while the PCE of the IUIC-O based OSC is only 7.66%. The higher PCE of the IUIC-T based OSC is mainly ascribed to its much higher J_{sc} (22.2 mA cm^{-2} vs 13.7 mA cm^{-2}). The higher J_{sc} for IUIC-T based OSCs partially results from its higher extinction coefficient, even though its optical bandgap is slightly wider than IUIC-O. Both IUIC-O and IUIC-T based devices afford decent FF around 0.70, indicating efficient charge transport and extraction in the devices. In addition, IUIC-O and IUIC-T have similar LUMO energy levels, but the V_{oc} of the IUIC-O based OSC is 0.03 V lower than that of the IUIC-T based one. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra of both IUIC-O and IUIC-T based OSCs are shown in Fig. 4b. The integral current densities for the IUIC-O and IUIC-T based devices are 13.1 mA cm^{-2} and 21.2 mA cm^{-2} , respectively, which are consistent with J_{sc} values obtained from the J - V measurement with mismatch within 5%. It can be found that the EQE value of the IUIC-T based OSC is much higher than that of IUIC-O based one in the whole region of 300-850 nm. For the IUIC-T based OSC, the highest EQE value of 75.7% is located at 730 nm, while the IUIC-O based OSC only afford a highest EQE value of 52.2% at 600 nm. Moreover, the IUIC-O based OSC only obtains EQE value around 35% in the range of 700-850 nm (corresponding to the strong absorption region of IUIC-O), which is remarkably lower than the

response value in the short wavelength region (corresponding to the absorption of PBDB-T).

The exciton/charge dynamics of the IUIC-O and IUIC-T based devices were conducted to investigate the reasons for the difference in photovoltaic parameters. The photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the neat films and D/A blend films were measured to explore the exciton dissociation in the blends, as shown in Fig. S5. The selected excitation wavelength for PBDB-T is 622 nm. The neat film of PBDB-T exhibits strong PL in the range of 650-850 nm. For the blend films of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T, the emission is almost all quenched (by over 98%), indicating effective electron transfer from donor to acceptors. For both acceptors, the selected excitation wavelength is 800 nm. For the neat films of IUIC-O and IUIC-T, the strong PL appear in 900-1100 nm and 850-1050 nm, respectively. For the blend films of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T, PL are quenched by 15% and 85%, respectively. It indicates that the hole transfer from IUIC-T to PBDB-T is efficient, while the hole transfer in PBDB-T:IUIC-O case is inefficient, which is due to the zero HOMO energy level off-set between IUIC-O and PBDB-T for inadequate charge transfer driving force. As a result, EQE response of PBDB-T:IUIC-O OSC in the range of 700-850 nm dramatically decreases. We further investigated electroluminescence quantum efficiency (EQE_{EL}) of the OSCs. EQE_{EL} of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T OSCs are 9.0×10^{-6} and 2.3×10^{-5} , respectively (Fig. S6). According to the formula ($\Delta E_3 = -kT \ln(\text{EQE}_{EL})$), the energy loss from non-radiative recombination, ΔE_3 , in PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T OSCs are 0.301 eV and 0.277 eV, respectively. The higher ΔE_3 in PBDB-T:IUIC-O OSC leads to its lower V_{oc} .

The charge recombination was explored via studying the dependence of J_{sc} and V_{oc} on the incident light intensities (P_{light}),

Fig. 5 Dependence of J_{sc} (a) and V_{oc} (b) on light intensity for PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T based OSCs.

Fig. 6 AFM phase images (a, d), TEM images (b, e) and 2D GIWAXS patterns (c, f) of PBDB-T:IUIC-O (upper) and PBDB-T:IUIC-T (bottom) blend films; (g) GIWAXS intensity profiles along the in-plane and out-of-plane directions of the neat and blend films.

respectively.²⁹ As for bimolecular recombination, their J_{SC} as a function of P_{light} was described by fitting to the power law: $J_{SC} \propto P_{light}^{\alpha}$ (Fig. 5a).³⁰ The exponent α for IUIC-O and IUIC-T based devices are 0.989 and 0.984, respectively. Both α values are close to 1, suggesting weak bimolecular recombination in both OSCs, which is beneficial for high FF. And we further studied monomolecular recombination in PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T OSCs via treating the V_{OC} as a function of P_{light} . The V_{OC} data were plotted against $\ln P_{light}$ (Fig. 5b).³¹⁻³³ The slope for PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T based devices are $1.57 \text{ kT}/q$ and $1.17 \text{ kT}/q$, respectively. The smaller slope indicates the less monomolecular recombination in the device.³¹ Thus the PBDB-T:IUIC-O OSCs suffer more severe monomolecular recombination, which is mainly ascribed to the inefficient exciton dissociation. The space-charge-limit-current (SCLC) method was conducted to measure the electron mobility (Fig. S7).³⁴⁻³⁶ The electron mobilities of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films are 1.25×10^{-4} and $1.60 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. The higher electron mobility of PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend film contributes to charge transport for its higher J_{SC} in OSCs.

The morphology of the active layer based on IUIC-O and IUIC-T were studied by atomic force microscopy (AFM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS), respectively. In the AFM height images (Fig. S8), the root-mean-square (RMS) roughness of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films are 8.19 nm and 7.58 nm, respectively. In the AFM phase images, both PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films show obvious nanofibril structure, which facilitates charge transport and inhibits bimolecular recombination (Fig. 6a and 6d). Moreover, it can be found that the nanofibril in PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend are narrower and finer, which contributes to the exciton dissociation and higher mobility in devices. And the TEM images of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films also exhibit similar nanofibril structure, which are in line with the AFM results (Fig. 6b and 6e).

The 2D GIWAXS patterns of the neat and blend films and the corresponding intensity profiles in the in-plane (q_{xy}) and out-of-plane (q_z) directions are shown in Fig. S9 and Fig. 6. All donor and acceptors in neat films prefer to a face-on orientation relative to the substrate. The π - π stacking diffraction peak in the q_z direction of IUIC-O is located at 1.76 \AA^{-1} , corresponding to the d -spacing of 3.56 \AA , while the π - π stacking diffraction peak in the q_z direction of IUIC-T neat film locates at 1.75 \AA^{-1} , corresponding to the d -spacing of 3.60 \AA . In terms of the Scherrer equation³⁷, the crystallinity coherence length (CL) values of two neat films can be identified that IUIC-O (2.81 nm) owns slightly longer-range π - π stacking than IUIC-T (2.41 nm). As for blend films, PBDB-T:IUIC-O presents a broad π - π stacking peak located at 1.76 \AA^{-1} contributed from both donor and acceptor. However, PBDB-T:IUIC-T shows (010) peak splitting, from which the π - π stacking peaks of PBDB-T (1.55 \AA^{-1}) and IUIC-T (1.72 \AA^{-1}) can be distinguished. It indicates a relatively immiscible nature of two materials. This is consistent to AFM results as pure phase, but smaller size, can be observed in the PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend film. The CL value of IUIC-T in the blend film increased to 2.59 nm indicating the enhanced π - π stacking, while the CL value of PBDB-T is 4.92 nm in the blend film of PBDB-T:IUIC-T and its π - π stacking is better than that in the blend film of PBDB-T:IUIC-O. In addition, a diffraction peak at 0.40 \AA^{-1} in the in-plane direction of PBDB-T:IUIC-T film, corresponding to the d -spacing of 15.85 \AA , which is ascribed to the (001) stacking peak of IUIC-T. It demonstrates that the orderly molecular packing along the conjugated backbone of IUIC-T in the blend film, facilitating the charge transport.³⁸ Overall, the favorable molecular packing of donor and acceptor in the PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend film helps to charge transport for the higher J_{SC} and PCE in OSCs.

Conclusions

In summary, two FREAs, IUIC-O and IUIC-T, based on a new undecacyclic donor core with different side chains were

developed. IUICT having 2D conjugated side chains possesses higher extinction coefficient than IUICO. Blended with the donor PBDB-T, the IUICT based OSCs achieve a higher PCE of 13.05% with a much higher J_{sc} , due to the aligned energy level with donor for efficient exciton dissociation, finer nanoscale phase separation and more orderly molecule packing in the blend film for charge transport. However, the PBDB-T:IUICO OSC affords an inferior PCE of 7.66%, due to the zero HOMO energy level off-set between IUICO and PBDB-T for inefficient charge dissociation, and the increased non-radiative recombination. Actually, IUICT is among the highest efficiency FREAs having such large donor core. This work demonstrates that developing large fused ring donor core is an efficient method to construct high performance FREAs and 2D conjugated side chains can improve the photovoltaic performance of FREAs efficiently.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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Author contribution

F.Z. and D.H. designed this project and wrote the manuscript. D.H. synthesized the FREAs and F.Z. conducted the device fabrications. W.M., J.X. and B.L. conducted the GIWAXS experiments and data analysis. J.Z., Y.H., B.L. and L.J. helped to analyse the NMR and AFM data. H.Z. and F.G. did the EQE_{EL} experiment and data analysis. Y.L. and C.W. revised this article. All the authors have discussed the results and commented on the manuscript.

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Highly Efficient Fused Ring Electron Acceptors based on a New Undecacyclic Core

Fuwen Zhao*, Dan He*, Jingming Xin, Huotian Zhang, Jixiang Zhou, Baojun Lin, Yongju He, Li Jiang, Wei Ma, Bao Li, Feng Gao, Yongfang Li and Chunru Wang*

Two FREAs, IUIC-O and IUIC-T, based on a large fused ring donor core (undecacyclic unit) were developed. IUIC-T, having 2D conjugated side chains, affords a higher PCE of 13.05%.

Supporting Information

Highly Efficient Fused Ring Electron Acceptors based on a New Undecacyclic Core

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- 1. General characterization**
- 2. Synthesis**
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- 4. UV**
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- 6. Device fabrication and measurements**
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- 9. SCLC**
- 10. AFM**
- 11. GIWAXS**

1. General characterization

^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were measured on a Bruker Advance-400 spectrometer. Absorption spectra were recorded on a Lambda 950 spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, U.S.A.). Cyclic voltammetry was done by using a Shanghai Chenhua CHI660C voltammetric analyzer under argon in a acetonitrile solution of tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate (0.1 M). A glassy-carbon electrode was used as the working electrode, a platinum-wire was used as the counter electrode, and a Ag/Ag⁺ electrode was used as the reference electrode. The polymer and acceptors were coated onto glassy-carbon electrode and all potentials were corrected against Fc/Fc⁺. AFM was performed on a Dimension 3100 microscope (Veeco) using tapping mode. TEM was performed on a Tecnai G2 T20 U-TWIN operated at 200 kV. GIWAXS measurement was performed at beamline 7.3.3¹ at the Advanced Light Source, Berkeley, U.S.A, with a Dectris Pilatus 2 M photon counting detector to detect the scattered X-ray. GIWAXS samples were prepared on Si substrates coated with ZnO. Two dimensional scattering patterns were collected on an in-vacuum CCD camera (Princeton Instrument PI-MTE). The beam size at the 5 samples is 100 mm by 200 mm.

2. Synthesis

All reagents were purchased from J&K Co., Innochem Co., HWRK Chem Co. and other commercial suppliers. Dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene, (4,8-bis((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(trimethylstannane) and (4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(trimethylstannane) were purchased from SunaTech Inc.. All reactions dealing with air- or moisture-sensitive compounds were carried out using standard Schlenk techniques. The compound **1**, ethyl 2-bromodithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate, was prepared according to the literature.²⁻³

Scheme S1. The synthetic routes for IUIC-O and IUIC-T.

Ethyl 2-bromodithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate. ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.40 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.31 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 1H), 4.46 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 2H), 1.49 (t, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 160.92, 142.59, 140.52, 130.15, 128.87, 126.85, 125.01, 120.65, 119.22, 61.59, 14.24.

Diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) (Compound 3a). To a solution ethyl 2-bromodithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate (730 mg, 2.1 mmol) and (4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(trimethylstannane) (772 mg, 1.0 mmol) in fresh distilled toluene (20 mL) in a two-necked flask was added $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (65 mg) under Ar. The mixture was heated to reflux and stirred overnight. Then it was cooled down to room temperature and added to 150 mL methanol dropwise. The precipitate was collected to give diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) without further purification (964 mg, 98%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.96 (s, 2H), 7.44 (d, $J = 4.7$ Hz, 2H), 7.35 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 2H), 4.45 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 4H), 4.35 (s, 4H), 1.75 (s, 2H), 1.46-1.25 (m, 22H), 0.88 (t, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 12H). MALDI-TOF MS (m/z): 979.3 ($\text{M} + \text{H}^+$)

Diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) (Compound 3b). To a solution ethyl 2-bromodithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate (730 mg, 2.1 mmol) and (4,8-bis((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(trimethylstannane) (904 mg, 1.0 mmol) in fresh distilled toluene (20 mL) in a two-necked flask was added $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (66 mg) under Ar. The mixture was heated to reflux and stirred overnight. Then it was cooled down to room temperature and added to 150 mL methanol dropwise. The precipitate was collected to give diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) without further purification (1.08 g, 97%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 8.08 (s, 2H), 7.42 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.37 (d, $J = 3.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.33 (d, $J = 5.2$ Hz, 2H), 6.91 (d, $J = 3.4$ Hz, 2H), 4.39 (q, $J = 7.1$ Hz, 4H), 2.87 (d, $J = 6.7$ Hz, 4H), 1.74-1.64 (m, 2H), 1.47-1.29 (m, 22H), 0.93 (m, 12H). MALDI-TOF MS (m/z): 1111.6 ($\text{M} + \text{H}^+$)

Compound 4a. To a solution of 1-bromo-4-hexylbenzene (1.21 g, 5 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL) was added magnesium (120 mg, 5 mmol) under argon, and the mixture was heated to reflux for ~1 h until magnesium disappeared. Then the Grignard reagent was added to a suspension of diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis((2-ethylhexyl)oxy)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-

diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) (490 mg, 0.5 mmol) in THF (10 mL) at room temperature under argon. The mixture was heated to reflux overnight and then allowed to cool down to room temperature. It was poured into water (~100 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ twice. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the residue was resolved in octane (15 mL) and acetic acid (1.5 mL) again, and the concentrated H₂SO₄ (0.2 mL) was added dropwise. The solution was heated to reflux for 1 h and then quenched with water. It was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ twice and the combined organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the crude product was purified via column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ (5:1, v/v) as eluent to give a yellow solid compound **4a** (345 mg, 46%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 8H), 7.27 (d, *J* = 5.3 Hz, 2H), 7.15 (d, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 2H), 7.05 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 8H), 3.61 (s, 4H), 2.53 (t, *J* = 7.7 Hz, 8H), 1.63-1.48 (m, 8H), 1.43-1.14 (m, 42H), 0.96 (m, 12H), 0.86 (m, 12H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 154.11, 149.91, 144.41, 141.71, 141.18, 137.86, 136.61, 136.22, 135.38, 134.59, 132.37, 131.44, 128.68, 128.17, 126.56, 125.41, 120.66, 73.35, 64.06, 35.57, 31.94, 31.70, 31.24, 29.65, 29.41, 29.15, 25.80, 22.77, 22.58, 14.18, 14.05, 11.24.

Compound 4b. To a solution of 1-bromo-4-hexylbenzene (1.21 g, 5 mmol) in dry THF (10 mL) was added magnesium (120 mg, 5 mmol) under argon, and the mixture was heated to reflux for ~1 h until magnesium disappeared. Then the Grignard reagent was added to a suspension of diethyl 2,2'-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)thiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)bis(dithieno[3,2-*b*:2',3'-*d*]thiophene-3-carboxylate) (556 mg, 0.5 mmol) in THF (10 mL) at room temperature under argon. The mixture was heated to reflux overnight and then allowed to cool down to room temperature. It was poured into water (~100 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ twice. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the residue was resolved in octane (15 mL) and acetic acid (1.5 mL) again, and the concentrated H₂SO₄ (0.2 mL) was added dropwise. The solution was heated to reflux for 1 h and then quenched with water. It was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ twice and the combined organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the crude product was purified via column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ (5:1, v/v) as eluent to give a yellow solid compound **4b** (220 mg, 27%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.10 (s, 2H), 7.03-6.90 (m, 18H), 6.46 (s, 2H), 6.13 (dd, *J* = 3.04, 7.49 Hz, 2H), 2.80-2.69 (m, 4H), 2.54 (d, *J* = 6.34 Hz, 8H), 1.58 (s, 10H), 1.38-1.27 (m, 40H), 0.99 (m, 12H), 0.88 (m, 12H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 149.53, 146.28, 146.22, 141.34, 141.13, 141.09, 136.55, 135.25, 135.18, 134.87, 130.30, 128.46, 128.43, 128.40, 128.38, 128.22, 128.15, 128.01, 124.46, 124.33, 120.53, 63.63, 41.52, 41.29, 35.62, 35.50, 34.21, 34.07, 32.52, 31.77, 31.45, 29.70,

29.21, 29.16, 28.88, 28.83, 25.76, 25.68, 23.24, 23.15, 22.65, 22.63, 14.32, 14.29, 14.11, 10.93, 10.79.

Compound 5a. To a solution of compound **4a** (300 mg, 0.20 mmol) in dry THF (20 mL) was added 1.6M *n*-butyllithium (0.50 mL, 0.8 mmol) at -78 °C under argon, and it stirred at the temperature for ~1 h. Then the solution was warmed to -50 °C. Anhydrous DMF (0.50 mL) was added to the solution and it continued to stir at -50 °C for ~1 h. Then it was quenched with water and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ several times. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the crude product was purified via column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ (1:1, v/v) as eluent to give a red solid compound **5a** (283 mg, 91%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 9.86 (s, 2H), 7.75 (s, 2H), 7.37 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 8H), 7.06 (d, *J* = 8.2 Hz, 8H), 3.63 (s, 4H), 2.53 (m, 8H), 1.61-1.49 (m, 10H), 1.38-1.13 (m, 40H), 0.95 (m, 12H), 0.85 (m, 12H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 182.47, 153.91, 151.65, 144.77, 142.97, 142.11, 140.77, 140.48, 139.54, 138.56, 137.70, 135.97, 134.92, 132.16, 129.98, 128.56, 128.33, 126.79, 73.51, 64.16, 35.55, 31.93, 31.67, 31.23, 29.63, 29.39, 29.12, 25.79, 22.76, 22.57, 14.17, 14.04, 11.22.

Compound 5b. To a solution of compound **4b** (200 mg, 0.12 mmol) in dry THF (15 mL) was added 1.6M *n*-butyllithium (0.30 mL, 0.48 mmol) at -78 °C under argon, and it stirred at the temperature for ~1 h. Then the solution was warmed to -50 °C. Anhydrous DMF (0.30 mL) was added to the solution and it continued to stir at -50 °C for ~1 h. Then it was quenched with water and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ several times. The organic phase was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. After removing the solvent, the crude product was purified via column chromatography (silica gel) using petroleum ether/CH₂Cl₂ (1:1, v/v) as eluent to give a red solid compound **5b** (177 mg, 87%). ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 9.82 (s, 2H), 7.71 (s, 2H), 7.04-6.93 (m, 16H), 6.47 (s, 2H), 6.13 (m, 2H), 2.75 (m, 4H), 2.55 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz 8H), 1.58 (s, 8H), 1.36 (m, 42H), 0.98 (m, 12H), 0.87 (m, 12H). ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 182.44, 155.69, 152.31, 150.11, 146.63, 146.57, 142.97, 141.72, 141.51, 141.47, 140.49, 139.54, 139.01, 138.52, 136.14, 134.58, 134.51, 135.25, 130.84, 130.44, 129.82, 128.39, 128.16, 128.08, 128.01, 125.16, 124.53, 124.40, 63.61, 41.52, 41.30, 35.60, 35.48, 34.18, 34.03, 32.49, 31.74, 31.44, 29.18, 29.13, 28.86, 28.81, 25.76, 25.65, 23.23, 23.14, 22.64, 22.62, 14.32, 14.29, 14.10, 10.91, 10.79.

IUIC-O. To a solution of compound **5a** (80 mg, 51 μmol) in CHCl₃ (10 mL) were added 2-(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-1-ylidene)malononitrile (59 mg, 0.25 mmol) and pyridine (1 mL). It was heated to reflux for 1 h and then cooled down to room temperature. The solution was poured into column chromatography (silica gel) directly and the crude product

was purified by using CHCl_3 as eluent to give a dark solid IUIC-O (86 mg, 85%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 8.87 (s, 2H), 8.52 (dd, $J = 9.8, 6.6$ Hz, 2H), 7.90 (s, 2H), 7.66 (t, $J = 7.5$, 4H), 7.37 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 8H), 7.08 (d, $J = 8.2$ Hz, 8H), 3.65 (s, 4H), 2.54 (m, 8H), 1.56 (m, 8H), 1.37-1.18 (m, 42H), 0.96 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 12H), 0.85 (t, $J = 6.4$, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 186.06, 158.12, 155.75, 154.33, 153.30, 146.74, 145.14, 143.31, 143.15, 142.70, 142.37, 138.08, 137.75, 137.72, 136.63, 135.50, 135.25, 134.46, 132.59, 128.50, 128.46, 127.13, 120.98, 115.02, 114.82, 114.32, 114.27, 112.68, 112.48, 73.65, 69.43, 64.25, 35.55, 31.93, 31.67, 31.23, 29.71, 29.62, 29.40, 29.11, 25.79, 22.76, 22.57, 14.18, 14.04. MALDI-TOF MS (m/z): 1979.7 (M^+).

IUIC-T. To a solution of compound **5b** (80 mg, 47 μmol) in CHCl_3 (10 mL) were added 2-(5,6-difluoro-3-oxo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-inden-1-ylidene)malononitrile (55 mg, 0.24 mmol) and pyridine (1 mL). It was heated to reflux for 1 h and then cooled down to room temperature. The solution was poured into column chromatography (silica gel) directly and the crude product was purified by using CHCl_3 as eluent to give a dark solid IUIC-T (88 mg, 89%). ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz, δ/ppm): 8.84 (s, 2H), 8.51 (m, 2H), 7.84 (s, 2H), 7.64 (t, $J = 7.3$ Hz, 2H), 6.96 (m, 16H), 6.48 (s, 2H), 6.14 (s, 2H), 2.72 (m, 4H), 2.56 (s, 8H), 1.56 (a, 8H), 1.49-1.24 (m, 42H), 1.00 (d, $J = 6.1$ Hz, 12H), 0.88 (d, $J = 5.0$ Hz, 12H). ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz, δ/ppm): 185.99, 158.11, 156.02, 153.40, 150.72, 146.91, 146.81, 146.65, 142.61, 142.41, 142.38, 141.98, 141.76, 141.61, 138.05, 137.74, 137.58, 136.58, 134.46, 134.12, 133.80, 132.99, 131.04, 130.58, 128.50, 128.28, 128.04, 127.98, 125.64, 124.63, 120.98, 114.30, 114.24, 112.65, 63.71, 41.53, 41.34, 35.60, 35.48, 34.20, 34.01, 32.54, 31.74, 31.44, 29.70, 29.25, 29.12, 28.87, 25.79, 25.69, 23.25, 23.17, 22.65, 22.62, 14.35, 14.31, 14.10, 10.92, 10.79. MALDI-TOF MS (m/z): 2112.6 ($\text{M} + \text{H}^+$).

3. NMR spectra

Fig. S1 ¹H NMR spectrum of IUIC-O.

Fig. S2 ¹H NMR spectrum of IUIC-T.

4. UV

Fig. S3 Absorption spectra of IUIC-O and IUIC-T in CHCl_3 (10^{-5} M).

5. CV

Fig. S4 Cyclic voltammograms of PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T.

Table S1. Optical and electrochemical data of PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T.

	$\lambda_{\text{sol.}}$ [nm]	λ_{film} [nm]	λ_{onset} [nm]	$E_{\text{g}}^{\text{opt}}$ [eV] ^a	HOMO [eV]	LUMO [eV]	E_{g}^{ec} [eV] ^b
PBDB-T	-	622	686	1.81	-5.16	-3.02	2.14
IUIC-O	768	812	928	1.34	-5.16	-3.93	1.23
IUIC-T	757	795	902	1.37	-5.26	-3.92	1.34

^a $E_{\text{g}}^{\text{opt}} = 1240/\lambda_{\text{onset}}$; ^b $E_{\text{g}}^{\text{ec}} = \text{LUMO-HOMO}$.

6. Device fabrication and measurements

Inverted solar cells

The ZnO precursor solution was prepared according to the literature.^[4] It was spin-coated onto ITO glass (4000 rpm for 30 s). The films were annealed at 200 °C in air for 30 min. ZnO film thickness is ~30 nm. A PBDB-T:acceptor blend in ODCB with additive was spin-coated onto ZnO layer. Then the film was annealed at 100 °C in N₂ for 10 min. MoO₃ (~5 nm) and Ag (~80 nm) was successively evaporated onto the active layer through a shadow mask (pressure ca. 10⁻⁴ Pa). The effective area of the cells is 4 mm². *J-V* characteristics of devices were measured under AM 1.5G (100 mW cm⁻²) by using a Newport Thermal Oriel 91159A solar simulator. Light intensity is calibrated with a Newport Oriel PN 91150 V Si-based solar cell. *J-V* characteristics were recorded by using a Keithley 2400 source meter unit. EQEs were performed in air on an Oriel Newport system (Model 66902) equipped with a standard Si diode.

Electron-only devices

The structure for electron-only devices is ZnO/active layer/Ca/Al. The ZnO precursor was spin-coated onto ITO glass and annealed at 200 °C in air for 30 min. A PBDB-T:acceptor blend in ODCB with additive was spin-coated onto ZnO. Then the film was annealed at 100 °C in N₂ for 10 min. Ca (~5 nm) and Al (~100 nm) were successively evaporated onto the active layer through a shadow mask (pressure ca. 10⁻⁴ Pa). *J-V* characteristics were measured in the dark and recorded by using a Keithley 2400 source meter unit.

7. PL

Fig. S5 Photoluminescence (PL) spectra of the PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T neat films as well as PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films excited at 622 nm (a), 800 nm (b) and 800 nm (c), respectively.

8. EQE_{EL}

Fig. S6 Electroluminescence quantum efficiency (EQE_{EL}) of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T devices.

9. SCLC

The space charge limited current (SCLC) was studied by using electron-only devices to find the charge-transport properties. The electron-only devices, consisting of active layer sandwiched between a ZnO coated ITO electrode and Ca/Al counter-electrode as the hole-blocking contact, were fabricated. From the current density as a function of voltage data, the electron mobility in the trap-free SCLC region can be estimated using the Mott-Gurney equation:

$$J = \frac{9}{8} \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \mu \frac{V^2}{d^3}$$

where ε_0 is the permittivity of the vacuum, ε_r is the relative permittivity of the material, μ is the charge-carrier mobility, V is the effective voltage, $V = V_{\text{appl}} - V_{\text{bi}}$, where V_{appl} is the applied voltage, and V_{bi} is the built-in potential which results from the difference in the work function of the anode and the cathode, and d is the sample thickness. Using this expression, the electron mobilities of IUIC-O and IUIC-T in the blend films were calculated.

Fig. S7 The $J^{1/2}$ - V curves of electron-only devices based on PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films (under dark).

Table S2. Electron mobilities of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films.

	μ_e [$\text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$]
PBDB-T:IUIC-O	1.25×10^{-4}
PBDB-T:IUIC-T	1.60×10^{-4}

10. AFM

Fig. S8 AFM images of PBDB-T:IUIC-O and PBDB-T:IUIC-T blend films: height images (left) and phase images (right).

11. GIWAXS

Fig. S9 2D GIWAXS patterns of PBDB-T, IUIC-O and IUIC-T neat films.

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